

ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF ADOLESCENT STUDENTS HAVING M-LEARNING HABITS IN RELATION TO THEIR INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract

M-Learning is an important instrument in the new Higher Educational Environment in the digital age which creates student-centred learning and educational practice, offering new more flexible learning methods. It enables connections and collaborations between individual participants and through their role as always-on, always-available, flexible personal communication devices. As mobile learning is becoming increasingly popular among adolescent students, it is important to understand how this mode of learning affects their academic performance. The aim of this research is to find out the academic performance of adolescent students having M-learning habits in relation to their intelligence. A sample of 200 adolescent students (100 boys and 100 girls) of +1 and +2 class studying in different schools affiliated to PSEB & CBSE, Amritsar was involved in the present study. Academic scores of final examinations were used for measuring academic performance. Group Test of Intelligence by Dr. G.C. Ahuja (2005) was used to measure intelligence. The findings suggest that (1) More than sixty percent adolescent students exhibit M-Learning Habits. (2) Significant difference exists in the Academic Performance and Intelligence of Adolescent Students having M-Learning Habits.

Key Words: *Academic Performance, Adolescent Students, M-Learning Habits, Intelligence*

Introduction

Adolescence is most critical period of human life, bringing permanent physical and behavioral changes in an individual. This period shapes the overall personality of an individual. The decision making at this stage plays a vital role in the life of adolescents- be it academic or daily activity or accepting their life style Academic performance determines the behavioral pattern of the adolescents. Improvement of academic performance of learner is one of the main objectives of educational institutions, because academic performance is essential for success and progress. Different factors such as individual learning styles, psychosocial factors, and

study habits influence academic performance of the students. The key to becoming an effective student is learning how to study smarter and not harder.

An hour or two studying of only subject textbooks is usually sufficient to make it through elementary schools with satisfactory grades, but when senior secondary education starts there are not enough hours or only subject textbooks to get good marks. It can only if you know how to study smarter.

Coming to this era of technological development the forms of resources has been distinctively transformed from printed books and journals to various electronic forms. Today's library has a challenge to broaden its resources and develop its collection in print resources as well as electronic format. Students of these generation are more inclined to digital forms of information as they like to get information in a fastest way.

Education is now moving from e-learning to mobile learning (M-learning) as mobile technology becomes popular in both formal and informal education(Jung, 2009).The importance of M-learning using various applications is among innovative concepts in terms of education. New generation which is known as "net-generation" explain their interests for online-learning and consequently m-learning. As mobile learning is becoming increasingly popular among adolescent students, it is important to understand how this mode of learning affects their academic performance. With the growing use of mobile devices, it is important to determine whether mobile learning is a beneficial tool for academic achievement or whether it poses challenges that need to be addressed. Adolescents who are emotionally mature are better equipped to manage stress, handle social interactions, and maintain a positive attitude towards learning, which can have a positive impact on academic performance. Likewise, intelligence is a key factor that determines the cognitive abilities of students and their potential for academic success. The aim of this research is to find out the academic performance of adolescent students having M-learning habits in relation to their intelligence.

The present study will provide an insight to the parents and teachers to deal effectively with their children, so that they will be able to develop an understanding of the importance of mobile technology for the students. This understanding will also assist the teachers to create student oriented practices in inculcating good study habits at school. Further, proper training and guidance may be given to the children accordingly to develop their self-concept, good study habits to improve the academic performance.

Consequently, the results of the current study may be extremely helpful to both students and teachers in resolving the numerous issues affecting their academic performance. The study will

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also be very important for students and teachers since it will provide them the motivation they need to actively improve their study habits, which are what determine how well they do academically. So, it has been deemed crucial to investigate Academic performance of Adolescent Students having M-learning Habits in relation their Intelligence.

Literature Review

Chaka and Govender (2017) executed research on “Students’ perceptions and readiness towards mobile learning in Colleges of Education: a Nigerian perspective”. The result revealed that the level of readiness of students increased more with an increase in mobile learning conditions. as compared to corresponding increases in performance expectancy, effort expectancy and social influence.

Wang et al. (2018) accomplished research on “Learning performance and cognitive load in mobile learning: Impact of interaction complexity”. The results showed that interaction complexity had an impact on students learning performance and mental effort in mobile learning: the higher the interaction complexity was, the higher mental effort and the better learning performance in mobile learning was there.

Aljaloud et al. (2019) carried out a study on “Saudi undergraduate students’ perceptions of the use of smartphone clicker apps on learning performance”. This study aimed to investigate how the use of a smartphone clicker app by a group of 390 Saudi Arabian male undergraduate students would impact their learning performance while participating in a computer science class. The results of the study found that the use of a smartphone clicker app promoted increased teacher-student and student-student interactivity, leading to active collaboration learning by students and improved learning performance.

Kaur (2021) conducted a study on “Academic performance of adolescent students having m-learning habits in relation to their intelligence.” The findings suggested that more than sixty percent of adolescent students were having M-learning habits. There was no significant relationship between academic performance of adolescent students having M-learning habits and their intelligence. There was no significant difference in the academic performance of adolescent students having M-learning habits in relation to their level of intelligence.

Objectives

1. To study percentage of adolescent students having M-learning habits.
2. To study the relationship between academic performance and intelligence of adolescent students having M-learning habits.

Hypotheses

1. More than sixty percent of adolescent students are having M-learning habits.
2. There is no significant difference in the academic performance and intelligence of adolescent students having M-learning habits.

Sample of the Study

A sample of 200 adolescent students (100 boys and 100 girls) of +1 and +2 class studying in different schools affiliated to PSEB & CBSE, Amritsar was involved in the present study.

Measures

Following tools were used for the purpose of present study:

1. Academic scores of final examinations will be used for academic performance.
2. Group Test of Intelligence by Dr. G.C. Ahuja (2005).

Results and Discussions

To analyse the data mean, standard deviation, correlation, percentage and t-test were used.

Following are the results.

Table 1: Showing Mean and percentage of all responses of M-Learning Habit Scale

S. No.	Sample	Mean Score	Standard Deviation	Percentage of students having M-Learning Habits
1	200	80.57	14.83	$166/200*100= 83$

Table 1 reveals that the mean score of M-Learning Habits Scale is 80.57, standard deviation is 14.83. Number of adolescent students having M-Learning Habit was computed by taking a difference of mean and standard deviation which is 65.74. A separate excel sheet was prepared by the investigator comprising of adolescent students who scored more than 65.74 marks on Mobile Learning Habit Scale. The total number of Adolescent students having M-Learning Habits comes out to be 166 in numbers. From the Table 1 it is observed that 83% students are having M-Learning Habits. So, the Hypothesis-1, "More than sixty percent of adolescent students are having M-learning Habits" stands accepted.

The reason for this may be that the increased use of mobile devices in education provides convenience, flexibility, and individualized learning experiences leading to the idea that more than 60% of teenage students have M-Learning habits. Peer pressure, parental involvement, and worldwide digitalization trends are additional factors that raise the probability of teenage M-learning.

Table 2: Showing Mean, S.D. and t-value of Academic Performance and Intelligence of Adolescent Students having M-Learning Habit

Variable	N	Mean	Mean Difference	Standard Deviation	Standard Error Difference	df	t-ratio	Inference
Intelligence	167	92.455		19.97				
Academic Performance	167	63.083	29.372	11.35	1.77	332	16.52	Significant at 0.05 level

A close scrutiny of the result inserted in Table 2 reveals that the mean scores of Academic Performance and Intelligence of adolescent students having M-Learning Habits are 63.083 and 92.455. The t-value is 16.52 which is significant at 0.05 level of significance. So, Hypothesis-II, "There is no significant difference in the academic performance and intelligence of adolescent students having m-learning habits" stands rejected.

The probable reason for this may be that students can participate in learning activities at their own speed and in settings that suit their learning preferences because to the flexibility and convenience that M-Learning offers. This individualized method of instruction may boost confidence and motivation, which will promote cognitive and intellectual development.

Educational implications

1. Mobile Learning offer constructivist learning Activities that encourage learners to actively construct new ideas or concepts based on their prior and current knowledge Should be introduced in curriculum. For example: M-learning allows learners to adapt existing mobile features to meet their needs, develop their interests, and construct their own learning.
2. Mobile technology offers new learning opportunities extending beyond traditional activities, allowing participation, challenge, and competition of participants. Hence it must be made part and parcel of teaching learning process.
3. Activities that lead to a change in the observable actions of learners based on learning. M-learning allows for actively controlling the acquisition process, this leads to an increase in learner motivation. In addition, mobile technologies foster self-directed learning, which encourages students to participate more actively in their learning process Hence, the rules, policies, and strategies of educational institutions must change perspective, providing opportunities for new approaches to active learning.

4. Mobile technology enables educational institutions to utilize a set of features such as flexibility, ubiquity, and portability in learning that will be of great benefit to teachers and students in the new digital era.
5. To take advantage of students' interest and the benefits of m-learning in education, educational institutions and their teachers should design innovative learning methodologies.

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